

Investigation of Nutritional Values, Sensorial, Flesh Productivity of Parapenaus longirostris (Lucas, 1846) Between Populations in the Sea of Marmara and in the Northern Aegean Sea

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Abstract : Abstract—The differences of *Parapenaus longirostris* caught from The North Aegean Sea and The Marmara Sea on proximate composition, sensorial analysis (for raw and cooked samples) and flesh productivity of the samples were investigated. Moisture, protein, lipid, ash, carbohydrate, energy contents of shrimp caught from The North Aegean Sea were 74.92 ± 0.1 , 20.32 ± 0.16 , 2.55 ± 0.1 , 2.13 ± 0.08 , 0.08% , 110.1 kcal/100g, respectively. Moisture, protein, lipid, ash, carbohydrate, energy contents of shrimp caught from the Marmara Sea were 76.9 ± 0.02 , 19.06 ± 0.03 , 2.22 ± 0.08 , 1.51 ± 0.04 , 0.33 , 102.77 kcal/100g, respectively. Protein, lipid, ash and energy values of the Northern Aegean Sea shrimp were higher than that of the Marmara Sea shrimp. On the other hand, moisture, carbohydrate values of the Northern Aegean Sea shrimp were lower than the other one. Sensorial analyses were done for raw and cooked samples. Among all properties for raw samples, flesh color, shrimp connective tissue, shrimp body parameters were found different each other according to the result of the panel. According to the result of the cooked shrimp samples among all properties, cooked odour, flavor, texture were found different each other as well. Especially, flavor and textural properties of cooked shrimps of the Northern Aegean Sea were higher than the Marmara Sea shrimp. Whereas flesh productivity of the Northern Aegean Sea shrimp was found 46.42% , the Marmara Sea shrimp was found as 47.74% .

Keywords : Keywords— Proximate value, sensory, *Parapenaus longirostris* flesh productivity.

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